

Federated decentralized trusted dAta Marketplace for Embedded finance

D7.1 - Dissemination and Community Building Plan (M4)

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Definitions

Acronyms	Definition
AAAI	American Association for Artificial Intelligence
AAI	authentication authorization infrastructure
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for IoT Innovation
ATOS	Atos It Solutions And Services Iberia Sl
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BPFI	Banking and Payments Federation Ireland
DAEM	Dimos Athinaion Epicheirisi Michanografisis
DAIRO	Data AI and Robotics
EC	European Commission
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FAME	Federated decentralized trusted dAta Marketplace for Embedded finance
IBM	International Business Machines
ICT	Information Communication Technologies
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IEEE	Institute (of) Electrical (and) Electronic Engineers
IJCAI	International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence
INNOV	Innov-Acts Limited
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Jrc Capital Management Consultancy and Research Gmbh
JSI	Institut Jozef Stefan
KM	KM Cube Anonymi Etaireia Parochis Ependytikon Ypiresion
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LC	Learning Center
MC	MC SHARED SERVICES SA
ML	Machine Learning
MOH	Motor Oil (Hellas) Diilistiria Korinthou A.E.
MVP	Minimum Viable Product Platform
NOVO	Novomatix Idiotiki Kefalaiouchiki Etaireia
NRS	Norsk Regnesentral

NUIG	National University Of Ireland Galway
PMI	Project Management Institute
SA	Supervisory Authority
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SW	SoftWare
TBD	To Be Determined
UBI	Ubitech Limited
UC	Use Case
UIA	UNIVERSITETET I AGDER
UNP	Unparallel Innovation
WG	Working Group
WP	Workpackage

Executive Summary

This document presents the Dissemination and Community Plan for the FAME project. It serves as common guidelines and useful information for the communication and exploitation activities that partners will and can carry out to achieve an effective dissemination of the project and its results.

The Dissemination Plan identifies all relevant channels, audiences, information and content that will be disseminated by the project. In addition, the implementation of this plan will optimize the involvement of the target group and relevant stakeholders, emphasizing the potential benefits that the project can bring.

The Dissemination and Community Plan includes the KPIs and the working methodology for the achievement of these indicators. This document reflects the collective and individual dissemination and communication actions, as well as events and workshops of interest.

This report introduces the FAME project branding. Building visual identity has been designed and built on the basis of the FAME consortium suggestion. This document is also developed giving the support to the communication and disseminating activities the FAME project Partners have to fulfil in – use the project logo, the colour palette and templates that have been developed within the project.

Dissemination and Communication are important issues within the FAME project. They are the pillars of the FAME approach in terms of targeting different groups and presenting to them the research results. For every category of identified stakeholders, the Communication and Dissemination strategy differs. However, the baseline message and brand remain transversal to all communication and dissemination activities.

The first version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan outlined the overall strategy and planned activities for the successful dissemination of the project results. However, necessary changes were added, in line with the feedback received from the first technical review of reporting period 1 (RP1). These updates are outlined in Section 1, Table 2.

This Dissemination and Communication plan and report is aimed at the consortium partners to ensure their involvement in all aspects of Dissemination and Communication, and the European Commission in order to communicate the consortium's strategy and report on undertaken dissemination activities.

The Communication and Dissemination plan comprises:

1. Dissemination and Communication strategy, including communication levels (EU/National/Regional) and the responsibilities/ roles attributed to each partner;
2. Initial dissemination content;
3. Initial list of target stakeholders to be addressed;
4. Dissemination channels: specifying the various tools that will be used to reach each of the target audiences;
5. Report on undertaken dissemination activities;
6. Dissemination materials;
7. Initial identified target groups and key actors.

The future versions of the dissemination and communication plan will also include the following sections, which are currently left out due to the early stage of the project:

1. Schedule and details of planned dissemination activities amongst partners, including a provisional list of events, conferences and fairs where partners can represent the project.

This document is the responsibility of INNEUROPE as the main partner of the project for the dissemination activities. Related to this document, Deliverables 7.2 and 7.4 will provide an update on the actions realized during each year of the project. D7.2 will cover the time from M1-M12 and submitted in the latter month. Then, these activities will be incorporated into D7.4, which will include the activities from M13-M24 and M25-M36 in the final submitted version.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	5
1.1.	Insights from other Tasks and Deliverables	6
1.2.	Structure	7
2	Communication and Dissemination Strategy.....	8
2.1	Dissemination Target Groups.....	8
2.2	Online Tools	9
2.2.1	LinkedIn.....	9
2.2.2	X.....	9
2.2.3	Website.....	10
2.2.4	YouTube.....	12
2.2.5	Newsletter and Press Releases	12
2.3	Offline Tools	13
2.3.1	Logo	13
2.3.2	Brand Manual.....	13
2.3.3	Brochure and flyers	16
2.4	Communication and dissemination channels	17
2.5	Key performance Indicators	17
2.6	Guidelines for Communication and Dissemination Activities.....	19
2.7	Guidance for Using Social Media	20
3	Communication and Dissemination Plan.....	21
3.1	Overview of Changes for Reporting Period 2	21
3.2	Communication and Dissemination Coordination	21
3.3	Individual communication and dissemination intentions.....	23
3.4	Communication and dissemination opportunities	31
3.4.1	European Events 2023	31
3.4.2	European Events Reporting Period 2 (M19-M36).....	33
3.4.3	List of relevant academic journals	34
3.5	Communication and Dissemination Calendar for RP2	36
4	Conclusions.....	43

List of Figures

Figure 1: Fame Twitter	9
Figure 2: FAME Youtube	12
Figure 3: FAME logo.....	13
Figure 4: FAME Isotype	13
Figure 5: FAME Logo 2.....	14
Figure 6: FAME Logo 3.....	14
Figure 7: Corporate Colours	14
Figure 8: Black and white LOGO version	15
Figure 9: FAME Logos Correct Versions.....	15
Figure 10: Logo Misapplications	16
Figure 11: Logo Sizes	16
Figure 12: Press Releases.....	20
Figure 13: Dissemination Activities	21
Figure 14: Communication Activities.....	21
Figure 15: Publications on Website	22
Figure 16: Scientific Publications	22
Figure 17: Target Groups.....	22
Figure 18: Standards	22
Figure 19: Dissemination KPIs Tracker.....	22
Figure 20: Communication KPIs Tracker	23

List of Tables

Table 1: Communication and Dissemination definition	5
Table 2: Revisions for Second Submission Following Review Report	6
Table 3: Target Groups	8
Table 4: Calendar for partner's content	11
Table 5: Group Calendar for partner's content II	11
Table 6: Dissemination Indicators	17
Table 7: Communication Indicators.....	18
Table 8: Dissemination Intentions	23
Table 9: Events 2023.....	31
Table 10: Events M19-M36	33
Table 11: List of potential scientific journals	34
Table 12: Monthly Communication and Dissemination Activity Plan RP#2 (M19-36)	36

1 Introduction

FAME, as a joint effort of world-class experts in data management, data technologies, data economics and digital finance, aims to develop and launch a single, reliable, energy-efficient and secure federated data marketplace for Embedded Finance (EmFi) to the global market. For a project of this scope, a powerful communication and outreach strategy is needed.

The general objectives of the Work Package 7 “Dissemination, Exploitation and Stakeholders” are:

- To disseminate and communicate the project’s results to stakeholders of the data economy, the European EmFi community and other relevant audiences.
- To build a vibrant community around the FAME marketplace.
- To contribute to the standardization and to policy recommendations about the evolution of the data economy in EmFi.
- To actively engage in DAIRO, GAIA-X and other relevant associations.
- To establish a learning centre for the data economy in embedded finance.
- To prepare plans for the exploitation of the project’s results.
- To create plans for the sustainability and wider use of the results.

With this Work Package we aim to spread the impact of FAME and its results to all the interested parties. Within this work package we are willing to inform, raise awareness, engage and promote the project to all possible interested bodies. This Work Package based on the Grant Agreement will present the overall communication and dissemination plan of the project. This plan has been created in order to maximize the audience reached during the lifetime of the project.

This deliverable (D7.1) includes the objectives of the work package, the target group, as well as the communication and dissemination channels and the KPIs. Likewise, this deliverable contains updates to the communication and dissemination plan for RP#2 (section 3), which are summarized in Table 2. This deliverable will present the individual and global communication and dissemination strategy of the project. In order to achieve this, we have identified the target people that we want to reach and the tools that will be used during the project so as to standardize the project’s message in order to have a high impact and achieve the objectives of the project.

Table 1: Communication and Dissemination definition

	COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION
Objectives	It covers the whole project and all results.	Promotion and awareness-raising of the results.
Audience	General public, including EU citizens, civil society and mass media.	Scientific Community, Open SW, AI BigData Communities, Fintechs, Banks, Citizens; SMEs; Policymakers; Insurance Companies; Embedded Finance Stakeholders in the Sectors
Language	Non-specialized language.	Scientific language
Channels	TV channels, radio, newspapers, website, newsletters, etc.	Peer-review journals, scientific conferences, online repository of results, etc.

Table 2: Revisions for Second Submission Following Review Report

No.	Section (Pages):	Description:	Relation to Review Report:
1	2.2.3 (10-11)	Section aligned with the website release 2.0 design. Partner groups table and monthly contribution calendar updated.	As a release 2.0 of the project website was suggested, this section was updated to reflect those updates. For more specifics on the version 2.0, please see Deliverable 7.2 (D7.2).
2	2.2.4 (12)	FAME YouTube link included directly into text.	
3	3.3 (22-30)	Individual communication and dissemination intentions updated to add/remove partners after grant amendments. Addition of strategic focus where appropriate (e.g., pilot focus).	This section was updated to add a strategic focus for communicating actions and activities around FAME's KERs (marketplace, LC, pilots, etc.). The individual communication and dissemination intentions for CAGS, EIH, and ETONEC were added.
4	3.4.2 (33-34)	Addition of FAME's list of strategic events for RP2.	To help guide the focus around the dissemination efforts of FAME and its KERs, the inclusion of an updated list of strategic events for RP2 was included.
5	3.5 (36-42)	Communication and Dissemination Plan for RP2.	This section outlines a comprehensive communication and dissemination plan for M19-M36, focusing on key moments in RP2, such as pilot progress, launch of the FAME marketplace, etc. Organized by Quarters, Actual Month and Project Month, it demonstrates the planned activities with indicative dates for each activity, including the channels utilized and partners involved.

1.1. Insights from other Tasks and Deliverables

Apart from identifying key stakeholders and prospective adopters by sectoral focus, we align our promotion per target group and dissemination channel or focused event accordingly. The key pillars of the dissemination strategy include:

1. Integrating and positioning the project into the European Data Economy.
2. Integrating the FAME marketplace into the EU finance ecosystem with emphasis on the EmFi segment.
3. Integrating FAME outcomes and tools within European communities e.g., DAIRO, GAIA-X, IDSA.
4. Engaging with relevant stakeholders in the EmFi pilots and attracting stakeholders from their sectors. Disseminating technical and scientific results to appropriate recipients and adopters; Engaging data providers, data spaces and data marketplaces towards expanding the FAME marketplace
5. Disseminating results about data assets pricing, trading and regulation to policymakers, governmental actors and finance/EmFi regulators.
6. Showcasing societal benefits of the FAME-based data driven economy.
7. Promote ESG Finance and investments as part of embedded finance.
8. Enhancing trust of the general public and SMEs in novel Fintech and embedded finance concepts.

The deliverables of this WP will reflect joint synergies, links and activities with affiliated projects, clusters, associations, real market industry links and identified project target groups, including a detailed plan for workshops, webinars, demonstrations and events.

Open access to FAME tools, Learning Centre trainings, videos and feedback will ensure wide promotion/adoption. In addition, the FAME ecosystem developed in DAIRO/ GAIA-X will be supported by promotional activities to reach a critical mass of registrants.

1.2. Structure

The Deliverable 7.1. "Dissemination and community building plan" is structured in four blocks:

- Part 1. Stages of the communication and dissemination strategy.
- Part 2. This part includes the objectives of these actions as well as the target groups that have been identified. We also specify the channels to be used during the implementation of the strategy and the presentation of the key performance indicators.
- Part 3 compiles the communication and dissemination timetable.
- Part 4. It includes the first actions undertaken by the project during the first 12 months of the project (M1-M12). The monitoring will be reflected in deliverable 7.2 and will bring together the progress for months 12, 24, 32.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

This section presents the communication and dissemination plan for the project. The following steps have been considered and will be further developed in the next chapter:

1. Identify communication and dissemination goals
2. Identify the target group
3. Channels used during strategy implementation
4. Strategies for Measuring Action
5. Indicative timeline for project communication and dissemination

The main objective is to promote the project and publicise its achievements to identified potential customers and stakeholders.

The communication and dissemination strategy of the project targets public and professional audiences. Dissemination and communication activities are carried out with a view to consolidate the visibility of the project among stakeholders and the general public at EU level and beyond. It is important to note that this Strategy foresees the design and implementation of different communication elements, such as media and materials (brochure, website, media, roll-up, etc.) to address dissemination.

2.1 Dissemination Target Groups

The following table lists the main target groups as specified in the Grant Agreement:

Table 3: Target Groups

Target Groups
Scientific Community: Universities and research institutes focusing on BigData/AI, Data Economy, EmFi, Data Trading/Pricing
Direct Industry Links linked to FAME use cases, as potential first adopters-potential customers: Links to EmFi Service Providers, Banks, Fintechs, Regulators.
Related-Affiliated Projects with similar activity and outcomes as FAME (e.g., BigData, FinTechs, Regulators)
Financial and Legal Actors, Policy Makers and Regulators
General Public and Media including retail customers/investors, SMEs, and citizens` groups
Associations, Clusters, Communities: BDVA/DAIRO (Digital Finance Group), GAIA-X, IDSA, Ai4EU, AIOTI
Open SW, AI, BigData Communities: Adopt and use the project`s open-source results
Standardisation Organisations: (e.g., ETSI, ISO, CEN/CENELEC, W3C, ISO, IDSA, GAIA-X)
FinTech Hubs and Innovators developing embedded finance products/services.

Scientific communities, Financial and Legal Actors, Policy Makers and Regulators, General Public and Media, Associations, Clusters, Communities, Open SW, AI, BigData Communities and FinTech Hubs and Innovators will be reached through the involvement of the consortium in the dissemination events (tentative initial list in paragraph 3.1) but also in sharing the FAME outputs in the appointed verticals to them via FAME social medias, web, and inviting them in future FAME initiative (workshops, etc.). Direct industry links will be created engaging the FAME Use cases ecosystems (WP6) in the process. In the case of the Related Affiliated Projects will be identified and also hooked

sharing the FAME follow up newsletter and also trying to join forces to organise common events. A list standardization organization has been already created and will be updated during the project span, thanks to the support of T7.2 Standard and SDOs Leader.

The target group contacts and their interest in the FAME Project will be listed inside the Excel table introduced into the Paragraph 3 and updated in the FAME SharePoint.

2.2 Online Tools

Online strategies are a main pillar in the communication strategy of the FAME project. During the project we will mainly use the project's website, social media and mailing lists to communicate and disseminate about the project. In the following section we will go into detail about the dissemination channels.

2.2.1 LinkedIn

Among the online tools of the project, we have the FAME LinkedIn. Through this page we will raise awareness of the project and the topic related to FAME in both LinkedIn but also in search engines.

All partners will contribute to dissemination tasks through this page, but it will be mainly administered by the Work Package 7 Leader.

Link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fame-horizon/>

This channel will serve as support for all the partners communication actions which are related to the FAME scope and purpose as well. The granulometry of the posts will at least the one described in the paragraph 2.2.3, but will be stimulated to rise more communication and media interactions and discussions for creating more “social noise”.

2.2.2 X

Another of the project's dissemination and communication tools is the FAME X account. The X @FAME_HorizonEU will be managed by the action's Work Package Leader, INNEUROPE.

The aim is to grow this community by posting relevant content and participating in various events across Europe and to disseminate daily news about the project.

Link: https://x.com/FAME_HorizonEU

Figure 1: Fame Twitter

2.2.3 Website

The FAME project website gathers all the basic and essential information regarding the project: <https://www.fame-horizon.eu/>

In order to generate a greater impact, all partners will be involved in the communication and dissemination of project outcomes and latest updates.

The structure of the website includes:

- **HOME:** the landing page gives a clear overview of the project, its objectives and who we are.
- **The project:** this section offers a further version of the unique features of the FAME Marketplace, the objectives and ambition of the project, the Work Packages and the Deliverables.
- **Consortium:** this section presents the logo of all partners involved in the project. By clicking on each logo, users will be redirected to the partner's official website.
- **Publications:** this section presents all the scientific articles and white papers created in the framework of FAME.
- **News and Blog:** this section will include all relevant FAME news and blog articles from partners and will be regularly updated with information coming from each partner. To achieve this, a calendar has been created and shared with all partners to keep track of each partner's contribution. To keep track of these contributions, the consortium was divided into four main groups.
- **Marketplace:** by clicking on this section, the website will redirect to the FAME marketplace.
- **Contact:** the contact section will allow interested parties to get in touch with us.

Following the release of a version 2.0 of the website, the structure of the website will transition to the following:

- **HOME:** the landing page of the project, providing the introduction to FAME, its innovative solutions (Marketplace, Learning Centre and pilot projects), and show the most recent news/blogs. Likewise, there will be a link to the subscription form.
- **PROJECT:** this new section will include the background and motivations behind FAME, an overview of the project's objectives, and include specific sub-pages for each of the seven pilots, the consortium of partners, and FAME's ecosystem (including backlinks for similar projects/initiatives and a pool of established stakeholders).
- **FAME PLATFORM:** this section will feature information on the FAME Marketplace and FAME Learning Centre, allowing end-users to learn about what is offered and including a call-to-action for users to explore each. There will be links included that redirect to the platform.
- **PUBLICATIONS:** this modified section will include all published project deliverables, scientific publications and whitepapers, and a communication kit for use by project partners and third parties.
- **NEWSROOM:** this section combines the blog and news spaces into one, allowing users to toggle by type of article or view everything simultaneously. Likewise, the events page will be included here (both past and upcoming), as well as another area to sign up for the project newsletter.

- **CONTACT US:** this final section will enable interested parties to get in touch with a project partner about the FAME platform, the pilot projects, or any other general inquiry.

The tables below present the four groups that have been created in order to organize the publications in the News and Events section.

Table 4: Calendar for partner's content

Publications	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11
Blog Website	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1
Publications	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20
Blog Website	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	Diss. Current content
Publications	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
Blog Website	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	Group 2
Publications	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36		
Blog Website	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1		

Table 5: Group Calendar for partner's content II

Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
GFT	DAEM	JOT	UPRC
FTS	JRC	INNOV	JSI
ATOS	MOH	TRB	EUBA
IBM	LXS	NOVO	UIA
ENG	UBI	NUIG	BPFI
MC	IQB	NRS	ECO
UNI	KM	NOVA	IDSA
INNEUROPE	UNP	AL	ETONEC
	CAGS	EIH	

The content for the blog (News and Events) should conform to the following characteristics:

- Include a headline
- 1,800 – 2,000 characters minimum
- 1 graphic or photo (highly recommended)
- Easy-to-understand language while avoiding very technical terms

The FAME website will also link to the project's social media channels. Visitors will also be able to sign up to the newsletter to keep up to date with the latest project news.

2.2.4 YouTube

The FAME project also has its own YouTube channel for dissemination activities.

Account: FAME HorizonEU

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCYeDY5xYON56tgegpLfcNoQ>

Figure 2: FAME Youtube

2.2.5 Newsletter and Press Releases

The objective of press releases and newsletters will be to accompany the whole life cycle of the project, marking the most important moments. This communication and dissemination strategy aims to keep third parties informed and different communication actions such as social media and mailing campaigns will be built in order to establish a solid database of recipients.

The FAME newsletter will be distributed to all partners involved but also to all people who subscribed through the project website. A total minimum of 12 newsletters will be published during the course of the FAME project. The newsletter will be built using the Mailchimp tool.

Newsletters and articles to present the research content in a more appropriate and attractive way for this type of media.

Press releases will be prepared to promote the most important events and results of the project. In addition, short interviews and visual media will be used to communicate results related to research and learning activities and dissemination events in an attractive and effective way.

All articles and digital newsletters published in mainstream and specialised media, as well as those published on partners' institutional channels, will be linked and disseminated through our social media platforms, such as LinkedIn.

2.3 Offline Tools

2.3.1 Logo

The FAME logo is a point of identification and a means of conveying the values of the project, which is why it is a crucial component of the project. The project's logo has been chosen from 3 different proposals made by the communication agency of the Work Package Leader. All partners were invited to vote for their favourite logo.

The FAME logo will be used in the offline communication of the project as well as in the online communication.

Below, the logo finally selected by the consortium is included:

Figure 3: FAME logo

The logo is the brand identifier commonly used in all applications.

Figure 4: FAME Isotype

In the case of FAME, the logo, or brand symbol, is the reduced version of the logotype, using only the "F".

2.3.2 Brand Manual

The Corporate Identity Manual includes the constituent elements of FAME's Visual Identity.

As constituent elements, we establish the construction guidelines, the use of typographies and the chromatic applications of the brand.

The consolidation of FAME's image requires special attention to the recommendations set out in this manual, as a document that guarantees a unity of criteria in our communication and public dissemination.

The Brand Manual must therefore be a "living" tool that is present in all applications of the corporate brand and its coexistence with its products.

2.3.2.1 Basic symbology

To avoid undesired results in the implementation of the Fame brand, a number of generic rules must be followed.

The Fame brand is constructed on the basis of a corporate logo, colours and typography that must be respected in any application.

applications.

2.3.2.1.1 Structure and security area

The Fame logo is inscribed in a rectangle in which the letters are correctly positioned.

The "X" value sets the unit of measurement. Thus, we ensure the correct proportion of the brand on any support and measurements.

Figure 5: FAME Logo 2

To ensure optimal application, a safety area has been determined based on the "X" value, which establishes a minimum distance from texts and graphic elements.

"X" value that establishes a minimum distance from texts and graphic elements.

Figure 6: FAME Logo 3

2.3.2.1.2 Corporate colours

Wherever possible, the brand should appear in full colour. In this case, the corporate colours shall be used.

For the application of the corporate colours, the four-colour reference should be sought for reproduction in print.

Figure 7: Corporate Colours

2.3.2.1.3 Corporate fonts

HK GROTESK MEDIUM LEGACY is the corporate typeface for titles.

It is used in its medium size to formalise the corporate image. Its use is defined for the design of titles associated with the company.

ROBOTO is the corporate typography for text.

It is used in all its versions to formalise the corporate image. Its use is defined for the design of text associated with the company.

2.3.2.2 *Rules for the proper use of the brand*

To avoid undesirable results in the implementation of the Fame brand, a number of generic rules must be followed.

The value of a brand depends to a large extent on the discipline of its application. In order not to weaken the visual message of the brand, it is essential to avoid counterproductive effects in its application.

A disorderly use of the visual identity creates confusion and has a very negative impact on the brand profile and on the public's perception of its values and services.

Ordering and applying the logo correctly is a guarantee that it will perfectly transmit the hierarchy within the corporate image as a whole.

2.3.2.2.1 *Correct versions*

Whenever possible, the main version of the mark shall be used. If this is not possible for technical reasons, the black and white version shall be used.

Figure 8: Black and white LOGO version

2.3.2.2.2 *Misapplications*

The logo has relative sizes and proportions determined by the criteria of composition, hierarchy and functionality.

Under no circumstances will these sizes, colours and proportions be modified.

Figure 9: FAME Logos Correct Versions

Figure 10: Logo Misapplications

2.3.2.2.3 Size Reduction

It can be reduced to a maximum width of 10 mm.

Figure 11: Logo Sizes

2.3.3 Brochure and flyers

A FAME brochure has been designed and uploaded to the project's SharePoint. This template will be available in the repository for use by partners. As needed, other brochures will be made available that have a more targeted scope.

2.4 Communication and dissemination channels

The FAME consortium is composed of different and complementary profiles, therefore different channels of communication and dissemination have been identified as possible ways of communication and dissemination. Partners will contribute through the channels they consider most convenient.

The following list contains the possible channels used by FAME:

- Publications
- Scientific publications (e.g., journals)
- Articles (e.g., peer-reviewed journals)
- Technical reports
- Newsletters
- Organization and/or participation in events
- Workshops
- Webinars
- Hackathons
- Trade Fairs

2.5 Key performance Indicators

In order to achieve the project objectives, the Grant agreement includes a number of Key Performance Indicators that must be covered.

Below is the list of KPIs that will be used to monitor the actions carried out during the project.

For the social media (X and LinkedIn), we will monitor using their own statistical metrics. For the website, tools such as Google Analytics will be used.

Table 6: Dissemination Indicators

No.	Dissemination Measure	Reason	Engagement Action	Target KPI
D1	Organization/attendance to conferences/workshops	Attract adopters, promote FAME	Organized: 15, Attended >=30	>=1000 visitors, 10 speakers
D2	Common activities with affiliated projects	Make FAME a hub of innovation	Common workshops, dissemination actions	5 common events, 5 posts in CORDIS/other EC systems
D3	Workshop/collaborative schemas with similar projects	Devise common tools. Engage members	3 workshops	25 project synergies, 5 common products/services
D4	Industry links, synergies	Attract adopters/users	50 real market links	10 adopters, 20 trials/testers
D5	Open access exhibitions and demonstration events	Outreach non-specialized audiences	Demonstrate UC in lively/lightweight way	>=3 exhibition, >=2 demo days, >=200 attendees
D6	Onsite UC promotional demonstrations/workshops	Attract customers,	Short video media coverage, feedback	>=1 demonstration per UC

		Raise awareness		>=1 workshops per UC
D7	Online and/or F2F training/webinars on Use Cases	Ensure general public understands benefits	Non-IT savvy public & for Financial Orgs	>=10 webinar/trainings >=50 attendees
D8	Dedicated ESG Results promotion	Engage Decision Makers and Investors	Open day with UC and media presence	>=2 events / workshops
D9	F2F with Policy makers / Banks (National & EU levels)	Join FDS; Engage policy makers	Open day with Use Cases	>=2 events, >=8 speakers
D10	Promote FAME Marketplace and Tools	Feedback on project tools and services	Activate all partner and UCs networks	200 registrants, 12+ marketplaces linked
D11	Uptake by Fintechs & with example Use Cases	Raise awareness, attract users, receive feedback	F2F & online examples of provided material	20 synergies established
D12	Open access reports	Scientific support	Scientific publications	>=5 journals, >=15 conference
D13	Non-scientific reports	Adoption by SMEs	Trainings/Showcases	>=5 industry magazines
D14	Standardization liaisons	WG links, feedback	Common publications	Standards/organizations >=5
D15	Association liaisons	Banks, Fintech Hubs	FAME Webinars	Liaisons >50

Table 7: Communication Indicators

No.	Communication Measure	Reason	Engagement Action	Target KPI
C1	Project website with links to data assets & Tools of FAME	Ensure back-links/ recognition to website	Engage registrants, Recurring visits	>=1000 visits, >200 registers >=350 blog interactions
C2	Web/social content, blogposts, articles, whitepapers	Build visibility and community	Project progress events, news	Y1: >2/month, Y2: >3/month Y3: >4/month
C3	Live audience feedback and live survey in online events	Grow community, Regular engagement	Visibility of project in all channels	1 live audience survey in online event >= 50 responders
C4	Digital liaisons with projects	FAME to be a hub of innovation	Link with Clusters	>=20 backlinks to website >=10 common articles/posts
C5	Videos, YouTube channel	Visually engage users	Promo video of UCs	1 promo/UC/tool, total >10

C6	Social media: ResearchGate, LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter,	Digital presence, new leads for synergies	Identify and regularly publish new content	>=3000 followers, >=500 posts, >=4000 interactions
C7	Marketing pack and promotional press kit	Focused material (for stakeholders/events)	Exhibition, demo days, workshops	Rollup, brochure, banner, factsheet (interim and final)
C8	Project identity and branding	Achieve recognition and brand awareness	All F2F meetings and all events	Logo, colour-space, artboard, graphic visuals, pitch, e-card
C9	Press releases, newsletters, and digital briefs	Send tailored messages to specific audiences	Communicate project's Benefits	Y1: >=8, Y2: >=16 (1/UC) Y3: >=24 (1/UC + 1/tool)
C10	Stakeholders' database and engagement tracker	Marketplace members, prospective clients	Develop a database of contacts and liaisons	Y1: >=500, Y2: >=1500, Y3: >=3500

2.6 Guidelines for Communication and Dissemination Activities

As specified in the Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement: “Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

- The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.
- Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.
- When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos”.

Moreover, according to Article 17.3, any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. It also should include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must therefore:

(a) display the EU emblem and

(b) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101092639”.

Press releases and newsletters will be issued as an average of one per month using the FAME Webpage as a catalyst for it. Any information (publication, use case event, tools development, meetings, etc) will be used for creating contents to be broadcasted. A table for that has also been created in the same Excel added in the SharePoint.

Press release, newsletter, etc.				
Nº	Name	Type	Link	Comments

Figure 12: Press Releases

2.7 Guidance for Using Social Media

Regarding Communication and dissemination activities FAME will be using the Horizon Europe’s guidelines on Dissemination and Exploitation

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm and <https://rea.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/Communication%2C%20Dissemination%20and%20%20Exploitation-2021.pdf>

The EU emblem can be downloaded from the Europa website: https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

3 Communication and Dissemination Plan

3.1 Overview of Changes for Reporting Period 2

Section 3 Communication and Dissemination Plan, includes important changes that were made following the Technical Review of Reporting Period 1. In Section 3.3 Individual communication and dissemination intentions, the requested changes have been made directly within the text, editing what was included in the originally submitted deliverable to highlight where communication and dissemination efforts will be focused moving forward. Section 3.4.2 European Events 2024-2025 is a new edition to this deliverable, highlighting a list of strategic events for FAME from the draft date of the revisions (November 2024) through the end of the project timeline. Finally, Section 3.5 Communication and Dissemination Calendar has been completely revised to reflect the Project Officer’s comments in relation to the RP1 Technical Review, incorporating indicative dates for various communication/dissemination KPIs.

3.2 Communication and Dissemination Coordination

The communication and dissemination activities carried out by each partner will be monitored on a regular basis every six months.

A table within SharePoint will be made available to all partners in order to record all dissemination and communication activities carried out by the consortium partners during the designated period.

This table will be reported within all versions of D7.2. as mentioned within the Description of Action (DoA). All consortium partners will be asked to fill in the Dissemination and Activity Report form after each dissemination activity carried out, as well as for those planned in the near future. These will be included in the annex of the annual update of the dissemination and communication guide. The list of dissemination and community activities will contain the following topics:

Dissemination Activities M1-18								
Date	Location	Responsible Partner/ Author(s)	Dissemination Activity Name	Type of Dissemination Activity: please choose and report one from the drop-down-list on button next to cell	Target audience reached (n°)	Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Type of addressed audience	Status of dissemination Activity

Figure 13: Dissemination Activities

Communication Activities M1-18							
Date	Responsible Partner/ Author(s)	Communication Activity Name	Description	Target Audience	Communication Channel	Outcome	Status

Figure 14: Communication Activities

Group Calendar For partner's Content (Blog+Social Media)					
M3 March 2023	M4 April 2023	M5 May 2023	M6 June 2023	M7 July 2023	
Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	
GFT Fujitsu TS ATOS IBM ENG B.Santander MC Services Universo GC	Dimos JRC MOH LEANKCALE UBITECH INQBIT KM CUBE UNPARALLEL	JOT IM INNOV TRAILBLU NOVOMATIX NOVOMATIX Un. Ireland NORSK REG. UNINOVA	TEESLAB IIS EUBA LIA BPII ECO VERGAND I.Data Spaces INSOMNIA Arthur's Legal BV	GFT Fujitsu TS ATOS IBM ENG B.Santander MC Services Universo GC	
M8 August 2023	M9 September 2023	M10 October 2023	M11 November 2023	M12 December 2023	
Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	Group 2	
M13 January 2024	M14 February 2024	M15 March 2024	M16 April 2024	M17 May 2024	M18 June 2024
Group 3	Group 4	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4

Publications:

Headline
2000 characters minimum
1 graphic or photo (hardly recommended)
avoiding technical jargon (easy to understand for mass media channels)

Publications/Posts on Website and Social Media M1-18							
Partner	Country	Type of Activity	Description of the dissemination activity with link	Date	Target Groups	Impact (n#)	Evidence (Screenshots)

Figure 15: Publications on Website

Scientific publication list has also been included to support this process and the partners in carrying on this task:

Scientific Publications							
No.	Type	Title	Responsible Partner	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proc./Book	Date	DOI

Figure 16: Scientific Publications

Target group list also managed where the list described in Table 3 has been inserted into the type of selection, all the partners are involved identifying and engaging them in the several dissemination and communication activities:

Target Groups					
Nº	Name	Acronym	Type	Contact	Description interest

Figure 17: Target Groups

In the case of the standards a new list and also description on how to fill it has been appointed:

Partner	FAME Why?/task	Area	SDOs Body/Committee	Reference standards, protocols, systems (the SDO/standard)	Description	Importance for FAME	Do you have any recommendations to enrich the standard?	Is it used in FAME?	Which part of FAME is it relevant for?	Geographic scope	Link to the standard	Additional information
Partner involved in proposing the SDO/standard	Relevant to any	platforms, Quality, Data architecture, Data interoperability, Privacy and anonymisation, Information Security, Cloud Computing, AML, regulations, Communication	E.g. DIN, W3C, ISO, ICMA, NML, etc.	E.g. ISO 22739:2020, SCAT, etc.	Describe the standard	How is this SDO or standard relevant for FAME	Even if you don't have concrete recommendations at the moment, where do you expect that FAME can contribute to this standard?	Yes/No	i.e. which architectural layer, policy, technology, etc.	Worldwide, EU, specific country, etc.		Are you already involved in this standard or SDO? Or do you have additional comments?

Figure 18: Standards

At the end, there is the last table where all the related KPIs (dissemination and communication KPIs) have been identified for being able to track and control them during all the project implementation

Dissemination KPIs Tracker					
Measure	Reason	Engagement Action	Status	Target KPIs	Achieved

Figure 19: Dissemination KPIs Tracker

Communication KPIs Tracker					
Measure	Reason	Engagement Action	Status	Target KPIs	Achieved

Figure 20: Communication KPIs Tracker

This KPIs will be checked periodically and reported to all the FAME Consortium and coordination as administrative control/check process.

3.3 Individual communication and dissemination intentions

The individual actions per partner with regard to communication and dissemination are listed in the table below. According to the Subsidy Agreement, the above-mentioned tasks will be carried out during the 36 months of the project duration. During Reporting Period 2 (M19-36), communication and dissemination efforts will be centered around providing updates about and accompanying the progress related to the FAME Platform and Marketplace, as well as the progress of the pilot projects and their use cases.

Concrete actions include:

- Web/social content, blogposts, articles, whitepapers.
- Videos, YouTube channel, Digital liaisons with projects.
- Press releases, newsletters, and digital briefs.
- Dissemination of the Project to Scientific Community.
- Organisation and contribution to events, workshops and exhibits.
- Posts on partner's social media and websites.
- Presentations in national/international forums and workshops relevant to project results.
- Informal person-to-person meetings with relevant stakeholders.
- Publishing results in journals.
- Hackathons for fintech/insurance tech services.
- Internal communications including electronic newsletters, town hall meetings and innovation meetups.
- Dissemination in Joint Events.
- Publication in academic articles in high impact international journals.
- Distribution of Brochures.

Table 8: Dissemination Intentions

Partner Organization	Dissemination Intentions and Plans
GFT ITALIA SRL (GFT)	<p>As GFT is an international digital transformation solution provider, a main dissemination target for GFT will be the financial and insurance industry (including banking) starting with its existing portfolio of customers.</p> <p>GFT will engage in technology transfer networks to disseminate the FAME results (including lessons learnt) and their importance and use in growing the FinTech sector.</p> <p>GFT will promote the project's results mainly within its own client base and contacts in order to further the potential use and take up of the FAME technologies and services. GFT will also disseminate the results of the FAME project at a European level through some of its own strategic alliances.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Contribution to the project's general (top-down) dissemination strategy through blog posts, contributions to the FAME web-site, newsletter;

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Dissemination of the project through the web site and social media channels of the company; 3. Leading role in the synergies of FAME with other relevant projects in the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC sponsored by BDVA) based on joint events and communication actions, as well as knowledge sharing (e.g., DataWeek in June 2023); 4. Organization of customer and stakeholders' workshops. <p>GFT will organize FAME related events which already gathers BigData and IoT innovators.</p> <p>In all the above ways, GFT is committed to increase the number of participants to the FAME marketplace platform and associated ecosystem.</p>
<p>FUJITSU TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS (FTS)</p>	<p>Fujitsu plans to contribute to the dissemination in following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whitepaper: Publish a whitepaper outlining the technical architecture and benefits of the Smart Contract and Trading Mechanisms in the marketplace and share it with industry experts and stakeholders. • Social Media: Use LinkedIn to share our whitepapers, articles, and other updates like highlighting the benefits and use cases of the FAME with our network. We will also use this platform to engage with our followers and respond to questions and comments. • Webinars: In coordination with task leader, help in organizing webinars and workshops to educate potential customers and stakeholders on the advantages of the Smart Contract and Trading Mechanisms in the marketplace. This could include partnering with relevant industry organizations to reach a wider audience. • YouTube videos: In coordination with task leader, help in creating educational videos on topics related to our data marketplace and smart contract solutions, which will be hosted on FAME's YouTube channel. We will also create short and long format videos to provide updates on our project and engage with our audience. • Journal Publications: In close coordination with task leader, publish articles along with other FAME partners in relevant industry journals to reach a broader audience. • Conference Presentations: Attend industry events and conferences to network with potential customers and partners, and showcase FAME and its capabilities. <p>Corporate Website and Blog: Regularly update our corporate website and blog with news, announcements, and product updates related to FAME, with at least one post every 4 months.</p>
<p>ATOS IT SOLUTIONS AND SERVICES IBERIASL (ATOS)</p>	<p>Atos aims to effectively disseminate the results of the FAME project throughout the organization using various communication tools, including newsletters, internal webinars, Atos Innovation Week, and Atos Expert Community. This strategy will ensure that more than 100,000 technologists in over 70 countries worldwide are informed about FAME's progress and can share this information with a wider network of partners and customers.</p> <p>Furthermore, Atos plans to regularly communicate updates on FAME externally through its corporate webpages, social media accounts, and press releases. This will allow the company to reach a broader audience and increase the visibility of the project's accomplishments.</p> <p>Finally, Atos intends to disseminate the project's results in specialized forums, conferences, and industry events such as the IoT Week, FIWARE Summit, European Big Data Value Forum, and Data Week. Collaboration with academic partners may lead to the publication of articles in reputable journals and conferences, further increasing awareness of FAME's achievements.</p>
<p>IBM ISRAEL - SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY LTD</p>	<p>IBM is involved in the consortium via its research unit and as such, will aim to disseminate the results of FAME via scientific publication and talks at conferences and workshops, specifically those that target AI and business</p>

(IBM)	<p>process management as their main topic, e.g., KDD, IJCAI, AAAI, BPM, and ICPM. In fact, IBM is chairing this year's second workshop on Process Management in the AI Era (PMAI) at the IJCAI23 conference. This workshop aims at bringing together researchers from different disciplines to promote the synergy between AI and process management to address open scientific challenges.</p> <p>IBM has a rich tradition of not only exploiting research technologies in its own products, but also in contributing key assets to the open-source community. Accordingly, IBM will work towards promoting the evolving FAME assets to the open-source community.</p>
INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA (ENG)	<p>ENG is the largest IT company in Italy, serving over one thousand large customers worldwide as a system integrator and provider of custom ICT solutions. To maintain this market leadership, ENG is continuously engaged in an innovation process that translates the results of its research investments into market solutions and services thanks to the interaction between the R&I department and the company's Business Units. Moreover, ENG is full member of the Big Data Value Association (BDVA), of the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), of the Gaia-X European Association for Data and Cloud and of the FIWARE Foundation.</p> <p>In the FAME context, ENG will exploit its vast network of customers and associates to disseminate the project's results. In particular: A) ENG's corporate website will include information on the project, on its technological outcomes and on the lessons learned in pilot applications; B) ENG will liaise with international initiatives and associations (e.g., BDVA, IDSA, Gaia-X and FIWARE), improving the awareness of the project's results in all the relevant working groups.</p>
MC SHARED SERVICES SA (MC)	<p>The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes. As pilot leader, special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 1: FaMLy – A powerful financial recommendation engine for families, during the second half of the project period.</p>
UNIVERSO IME SA (UNI)	<p>The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes. Special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 1: FaMLy – A powerful financial recommendation engine for families, during the second half of the project period.</p>
DAEM - DIMOS ATHINAION EPICHEIRISI MICHANOGRAFISIS (City of Athens IT Company) (DAEM)	<p>DAEM's dissemination foresees the promotion and presentation of the project results while recruiting stakeholders at any relevant local, national or international events. DAEM's social networks will be exploited in cooperation with DAEM's highly skilled Marketing Department to serve dissemination purposes, along with its parental and sister organizations' networks. Indicatively, communities of citizens, decision-makers, local government organizations, governmental organizations, NGOs, academics, researchers, students, businesses etc. Special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 2: Embedding Finance Services in a Personalized Citizen Wallet, during the second half of the project period.</p>
JRC CAPITAL GMBH (JRC)	<p>JRC intends to disseminate FAME results through regular posts on the company's social media channels, websites and external partner channels. In addition, JRC will contribute by writing white papers to support the commercialisation of the activities and results of the project.</p> <p>In terms of targeting to make the FAME project attractive to the community, JRC will focus on creating collaborative workshops on the pilots to be engaged and deployed in the project, as well as some training videos focusing on the</p>

	<p>role of JRC and results of the project, including ESG portfolio recommendations, explanations on ESG scores, etc.</p> <p>Participation in collaborative publications, workshops and webinars for dissemination of the project will always be an objective of JRC.</p> <p>Special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 5: ESG Scorecard Ranking & Sustainable Portfolio Optimisation, during the second half of the project period.</p>
<p>MOTOR OIL (HELLAS) DIILISTIRIA KORINTHOU AE (MOH)</p>	<p>MOH plans to disseminate the project's outcomes through posts in its website and social media so as to communicate the progress and milestones achieved. Additionally, the project will be presented at relevant events/conferences that MOH may participate. As pilot 7 leader, special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 7: Assessing the Quality and Monetary Value of Data Assets, during the second half of the project period.</p>
<p>LEANXCALE SL (LXS)</p>	<p>LeanXcale will create awareness in the industry about the innovations developed in the project to prepare for large scale commercialization after project end. The targeted markets are Europe, Asia and US while the target groups will be sectors that are data intensive and rely on isolated silos.</p> <p>The dissemination of the technology developed by LeanXcale will use the following types of channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conferences / Exhibitions / trade fair • Webinars: bimonthly webinar related with the technology that LeanXcale is brining and developing within the project. <p>Press releases, newspaper articles and other dissemination activities: 1 monthly post on data management from month 13 till end of the project at LinkedIn network that counts today with 21,000 contacts in the first level, 4 million in the second level and 585 billion in the third level.</p>
<p>UBITECH LIMITED (UBI)</p>	<p>UBITECH's dissemination plan during the course of the project focuses on the diffusion of the project scope, objectives and developments to a wide range of stakeholders in the relevant business, industrial and research communities, starting from the preliminary and first results (e.g. conceptualization, framework, architecture, models) at the early stages of the project to more technological mature results (e.g. prototypes, software components, integrated platform, pilots, evaluation) near the end of the project. To achieve this, UBITECH plans to leverage a variety of dissemination channels including, among others, the following: (a) publication on its corporate website and company newsletter, (b) active participation to EU organized events and conferences, (c) scientific publications in topic-specific journals, conferences and workshops, (d) editing and publication of brochures, press releases and announcements.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hence, UBITECH plans to disseminate the project results to relevant actors and stakeholders in the information and communication technologies (ICT), Big Data (BDVA), and EmFI market, as well as in the overall fintech sector. To this end, UBITECH will target relevant journals and conferences such as the IEEE/ACM International Conference on Big Data Computing Applications and Technologies (BDCAT), IEEE International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA) and World Summit AI, as well as exhibitions and trade fairs such as the FinTech World Forum, the FinTech Connect and the Cyprus FinTech Expo.
<p>INQBIT INNOVATIONS SRL (IQB)</p>	<p>The dissemination plan of INQBIT during the project is focused on the publication of both the purpose and the technologies related to authentication authorization infrastructure (AAI) and security policies in which our company participates on a technical level. The means that INQBIT will leverage in order to achieve this purpose are the following: (a) regular posts on the company's</p>

	<p>social media which will relate to the progress of the project as well as the active participation of INQBIT within it. (b) Presentations of innovative technical developments and connections with other EU projects in conferences like ARES 2023 (c) Possible collaboration with academic partners with main purpose of publishing articles in reputable journals and conferences.</p> <p>INQBIT is a small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) focused on designing, developing, and delivering ICT solutions and services to the market. Through FAME, INQBIT aims to expand its knowledge of data security. This will allow the company to broaden its audience and increase the visibility of the whole project.</p>
KM CUBE ANONYMI (KM)	The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes. Special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 5: ESG Scorecard Ranking & Sustainable Portfolio Optimisation, during the second half of the project period.
UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA (UNP)	The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes
JOT INTERNET MEDIA ESPANA SL (JOT)	JOT's plan for dissemination combines the generation of content (short articles and press release) to promote the data monetization use case in social media as well as the publication of the most innovative technical developments in scientific journals and conferences like RuleML+RR 2023, Big Data & AI World and IARIA Congress 2023. As part of BVDA, JOT periodically in events like European Big Data Value forum.
INNOV-ACTS LIMITED (INNOV)	INNOV-ACTS will disseminate the project's outcomes through the following channels: (A) Blogs and posts that will be regularly published (i.e., at least once per month) in the company's web site and social media channels, including posts for the results produced by INNOV i.e., the Learning Center, the blockchain developments and the MoH pilot; (B) Presentations in conferences such as the IoT Week and the Data Week, as well as blockchain related events such as the Decentralized conference; (C) Publications in scientific journals and conferences such as the annual IEEE DCOSS-IoT conference; (D) Whitepapers aiming at the marketing and promotion of the project's outcomes to targeted stakeholders such as EmFi solution providers, financial organizations and policy makers; (E) Liaisons with organizations relevant to the project's results such as the EU Blockchain Observatory and Forum (EUBOF).
TRAILBLU YAZILIM ANONIM SIRKETI (TRB)	The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes
NOVOMATIX IDIOTIKI KEFALAIIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA (NOVO)	The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes. Special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 2: Embedding Finance Services in a Personalized Citizen Wallet, during the second half of the project period.
NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY (NUIG)	The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes
NORSK REGNESENTRAL (NRS)	NRS will use project results for educational purposes at (i) the University of Oslo, (ii) NTNU, and (iii) University of Bergen which are collaborating with NRS in education. NRS will target research communities, climate change main

	<p>stakeholders and players (government agencies, regulatory agencies, environmental industry stakeholders, and additional climate industry technology actors), Norwegian SMEs, Large organizations Norwegian and Nordic stakeholders, Universities and Colleges for dissemination. General outlets for reaching these audiences include science news outlets such as www.forskning.no which publishes articles in Norwegian and www.sciencenordic.com which publishes articles in English, as well as the science sections of Norwegian newspapers and NRS' own podcast series. We will in addition present the results of the project at climate adaptation conferences that aim to bring together researchers, public administrations and private actors, such as the European Conference and Climate Change Adaptation and the Nordic Conference on Climate Change Adaptation. NRS will disseminate new technology advances through high impact publications and conferences, as well as scientific forums. NRS will target some of the top AI journals as well as journals that operate on the intersection between statistics, AI, climate science, security and trust, and decision science. These include IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems, Foundations and Trends in Machine Learning, International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection, International Journal of Information Technology & Decision Making, Environmental Research Letter, the Journals of the Royal Statistical Society, International Journal of Information Security, ACM Transactions on Privacy and Security, IEEE Security and Privacy, etc. NRS participates in NORCICS (Norwegian Centre for Cybersecurity in Critical Sectors - https://www.ntnu.edu/norcics) where critical infrastructure resilience, identity and trust management are the key pillars, and finance is one of the important critical sectors. NRS is also actively involved in organizing workshops co-located with the ESORICS and ARES conferences where NRS will present and disseminate project results. NRS also participates in several national and international networks and clusters which NRS will present and disseminate project results. NRS will construct a project website for FAME on NRS' official website. As pilot 6 leader, special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 6: Embedding Climatic Predictions in Property Insurance Products, during the second half of the project period.</p>
<p>UNINOVA (NOVA)</p>	<p>The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes.</p>
<p>UNIVERSITY OF PIRAEUS RESEARCH CENTER (UPRC)</p>	<p>UPRC researchers will disseminate the results of FAME primarily through scientific publications in various conferences, workshops, and journals. Additionally, the university collaborates continuously with national organizations, including: (i) the General Secretariat of Research & Technology (GSRT), (ii) the National Documentation Centre (NDC), and (iii) the Technical Chamber of Greece (TEE-TCG). Collaborating with those organizations, UPRC will disseminate the results of FAME at a national level towards the general public and the industrial community being represented in the aforementioned groups. UPRC is also directly involved in various national and European research projects and collaboration groups, which will act as consumers of the project results through specific collaboration and communication activities. Finally, since UPRC is tightly coupled with the University of Piraeus – as its research centre, it intensively collaborates with all of its IT departments, and as a result the UPRC researchers will be able to actively organize training sessions / lectures in both under-graduate and post-graduate programmes to promote the project results and research outcomes.</p>
<p>INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN (JSI)</p>	<p>The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop</p>

	<p>or event aligned with the FAME purposes. As JSI is a research partner, the results of the project will be also disseminated through scientific publications. JSI is also involved in FAME's Training Programs, Learning Center and Stakeholders' Training, and this result will be also actively disseminated through JSI's networks.</p>
<p>EKONOMICKA UNIVERZITA V BRATISLAVE (EUBA)</p>	<p>The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes</p>
<p>UNIVERSITETET I AGDER (UIA)</p>	<p>UiA aims to effectively disseminate the results of the FAME project throughout the research community and to practitioners using multiple communication means including presentations in workshops, seminars and conferences, newsletters and research publications. Furthermore, UiA plans to regularly communicate updates on FAME through social media accounts and webpages. Finally, outcomes from the ongoing activities of FAME project will be used as real-life examples and input into relevant courses (i.e., Data Science Applications I, Data Science Applications II, Human-Centred AI, Research Methods in Information Systems).</p> <p>UiA will target both International Conferences and Journals:</p> <p>Conferences: I3E IFIP Conference - e-Business, e-Services, and e-Society European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS) Mediterranean Conference on Information Systems (MCIS)</p> <p>Journals: Information Systems Frontiers (Springer) International Journal of Information Management Data Insights (Elsevier) Behaviour & Information Technology (T&F)</p>
<p>BANKING & PAYMENTS FEDERATION IRELAND (BPMI)</p>	<p>The organization will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs regularly, also in any workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes. As pilot 3 leader, special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding Pilot 3: Personalized Collaborative Intelligence for Enhancing EmFi Services during the second half of the project period.</p>
<p>ECO VERBAND DER INTERNETWIRTSCHAFTEV (ECO)</p>	<p>eco – Association of the Internet Industry plans to organize the dissemination according to the following procedure. In the first year, we will present FAME to the outside world as a perspective use case based on the relevant specification (according to GXFS) and integrate it into the Gaia-X events. The goal is to create awareness, expectation and curiosity towards applicability among relevant target groups, multipliers and stakeholders. In the 2nd year we will - as soon as available - disseminate the interim results assuming that Gaia-X compliance will be achieved. FAME will thus benefit from the Gaia-X activities in the dissemination and in this framework. FAME's own topics will be provided with an appropriate audience. In the third year, articles and events will be more focused on applicability, transfer, testing and implementation (integration of DataSpaces and Marketplaces). We would use our own and third-party events for this purpose. Events, interim results, feedback and relevance for the target group will be flanked by articles and social media.</p>
<p>INTERNATIONAL DATA SPACES EV (IDSA)</p>	<p>IDSA will be disseminating FAME results through the IDSA magazine, events and online tech-talk webinars, in an IDSA update session and the events of other organizations we have close ties with. We will also be showcasing FAME in the IDSA use cases RADAR and through a blog article in our own web site. Finally, we will take the chance to amplify FAME press releases and events through our social media postings.</p>
<p>INNEUROPE INITIATIVE, S.L (INNEUROPE).</p>	<p>INNEUROPE will disseminate the FAME project results and outputs to our local, national, and global network of hubs, accelerators, and relevant startups, as well as Chambers of Commerce and other relevant actors (ICEX, etc.). As Innovation platform, we are co-leaders of The Talent Route (1st international</p>

	<p>accelerator network in the EU) and 100 Startups (a European Open Innovation program promoted by 10 European Hubs to boost start-ups' growth in some specific sectors like Health and Fintech); promoters of EURAFI (European Alliance for Fintech Innovation) and members of EIT Digital, EDIH and EYE, among other relevant innovation and start-up networks. As pilot 4 leader, special emphasis will be given to the dissemination of results surrounding the pilots, including Pilot 4: The EU Funds Application Process Made Easy during the second half of the project period. As WP7 Leader, INNEUROPE will provide generalized support and direction for all communication and dissemination efforts.</p>
<p>ARTHUR'S LEGAL BV (AL)</p>	<p>AL intends to promote the results produced during the FAME project by leveraging its own network of cities, EU member states, EU institutions, non-governmental organisations and other interested SMEs.</p> <p>Moreover, the results produced during the project will be disseminated at conferences, in the Netherlands and in Europe, in which Arthur's Legal will participate, also as a panellist.</p> <p>From time to time, AL will attend the relevant FAME webinars and communicate the relevant outcomes on its social media profile (LinkedIn), through blog posts and comments, as well as through Arthur's Legal and Arthur's Legal, Strategies & Systems websites, and the personal LinkedIn pages of colleagues involved in the specific activities.</p>
<p>CREDIT AGRICOLE GROUP SOLUTIONS S.C.p.A. (CAGS)</p>	<p>Credit Agricole Group Solutions will use internal and external networks for communicating and disseminating the FAME Project outputs, also in workshop or event aligned with the FAME purposes.</p> <p>Furthermore, Credit Agricole Group Solutions will organize specific periodic meetings with the corporate Functions responsible for creating the application infrastructures for the use of information flows and databases in general to illustrate the purposes, structural profiles and progress of the project.</p> <p>Finally, an overview of the project will be published in the company newsletter.</p>
<p>ELIS INNOVATION HUB (EIH)</p>	<p>ELIS will leverage different national or international events, workshops and LinkedIn articles or posts to disseminate FAME results, primarily in a national context. ELIS's target groups.</p> <p>In relation to their target groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn articles/posts: The entire EIH network as regards posts/articles, therefore a very varied target that covers any business area, from public bodies to private companies that can be a startup, a PMI or a large company. • Events/workshops: Companies interested in the world of AI, Big data or other possible companies, obviously belonging to the ELIS consortium and interested in the objectives of FAME. In our consortium we have more than 130 companies with core businesses in various fields, automotive, energy, banking, insurance, etc.
<p>ETONEC GMBH (ETONEC)</p>	<p>Etonec is a company working at the global intersection of payments, identity & digital assets. With clients around the world, the majority of them in the domain of regulated financial services, etonec advises and builds out Proof of Concepts in the areas of digital identity, digital assets and CBDCs as well as on payments and payment regulation.</p> <p>Etonec intends to disseminate the FAME project via multiple channels. Utilizing our network on social media platforms, such as LinkedIn and X or blog posts on our website. With our network spanning globally, we do not focus on a specific region but do have a big concentration of our network in Europe. Where suitable, etonec would also place FAME with existing engagements and mention during the many in-person engagements at leading conferences, where etonec executives are often requested as a speaker.</p>

3.4 Communication and dissemination opportunities

3.4.1 European Events 2023

The participation of the consortium in one of the following events, can be a great opportunity to give visibility to the project and to present it to other financial institutions, regulators, Fintech, etc. The following table summarises upcoming European events related to digital finance, FinTech, Data Science & Statistics, Big Data, etc:

Table 9: Events 2023

N°	Location	Event's Name	Date	Link
1	Paris	Paris FinTech Forum	May 30&31, July 4, October 10&12, November 28, 2023	https://members.parisfintechforum.com/
2	Frankfurt	World Conference on Data Science & Statistics	June 26-27, 2023	https://datascience.thepeopleevents.com/
3	Amsterdam	Money 20/20 Europe	June 6-8, 2023	https://europe.money2020.com/
4	Köln	The POST/Bank hackathon	June 3-5, 2023	https://www.hackathon.com/event/post--bank-hackathon-cologne-23939444523
5	Amsterdam	Blockchain Expo	September 26 & 27, 2023	https://blockchain-expo.com/europe/
6	Valencia	European Big Data Value Vlc	October 25-27, 2023	https://www.bdva.eu/european-big-data-value-forum-ebdvf-2023
7	Luleå, Sweden	European Big Data Value Data Week 2023	June 13-15, 2023	https://data-week.eu/
8	Macao, China	2nd Process Management in the AI Era (PMAI)	19-21/08/2023	https://pmai23.github.io
9	Pafos	IEEE DCROSS-IoT 2023	19-21/06/2023	https://dcross.org/

10	London	FinTech Connect 2023	06-07/12/2023	https://www.fintechconnect.com/events-london
11	Thessaloniki	IEEE International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)	09-13/10/2023	https://conferences.sigappfr.org/dsaa2023/
12	Benevento	2023 International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security (ARES)	August 29 – September 1, 2023	https://www.ares-conference.eu/
13	The Hague	The 28th European Symposium on Research in Computer Security (ESORICS)	September 25-29, 2023	https://esorics2023.org/
14	Exeter	The 22nd IEEE International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications (TrustCom)	Nov 1-3, 2023	https://hpcn.exeter.ac.uk/trustcom2023/
15	Frankfurt	Digital Euro Conference 2023 - #DEC23	31 March 2023	https://blog.digital-euro-association.de/the-digital-euro-conference-2023-summary
16	Benevento	2023 International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security (ARES),	September 1, 2023	https://www.ares-conference.eu/
17	The Hague	The 28th European Symposium on Research in Computer Security (ESORICS)	25-29, 2023	https://esorics2023.org/
18	Exeter	The 22nd IEEE International Conference on Trust, Security and Privacy in Computing and Communications	Nov 1-3, 2023	https://hpcn.exeter.ac.uk/trustcom2023/
19	Kristiansand, Norway	The 31 st European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS)	Jun 11-16, 2023	https://ecis2023.no/
20	Curitiba, Brazil	The 22th IFIP Conference e-Business, e-Services, and e-Society I3E2023	Nov 9-11, 2023	https://www.i3e2023.com/
21	Istanbul	SmartNets 2023 - International Conference on Smart Applications,	July 25-27, 2023	https://smartnets.ieee.tn/

		Communications and Networking		
22	Slovenia	26th International Multiconference Information Society. Conference: SIKDD DATA MINING AND DATA WAREHAUSES	October 9-13., 2023	https://is.ijs.si/?lang=en

3.4.2 European Events Reporting Period 2 (M19-M36)

During the second half of the project lifetime (M19-M36), many of FAME's objectives will have demonstrable, verifiable results. The FAME Platform will be in its final integration phases prior to deployment, the Learning Center will have gathered course material and generated course content, and the seven FAME pilot projects will have different levels of progress made, many being ready for advanced dissemination efforts. For that reason, it is important to attend European events within the Big Data and AI, digital finance and banking, FinTech, and data spaces sectors. Below is a list of strategic European events for this reporting period. This is a preliminary, non-exhaustive list that will be regularly updated by INNEUROPE and project partners are more events and opportunities to present FAME are made aware.

Table 10: Events M19-M36

No.	Start Date	End Date	Event + Link	Location
1	2-Oct-24	4-Oct-24	European Big Data Value Forum 2024	Budapest, Hungary
2	22-Oct-24	23-Oct-24	MoneyLIVE Nordic Banking	Copenhagen, Denmark
3	22-Oct-24	24-Oct-24	Finweek Bratislava 2024	Bratislava, Slovakia
4	23-Oct-24	24-Oct-24	Valencia Digital Summit 2024	Valencia, Spain
5	29-Oct-24	29-Oct-24	Vi Financial & Fintech Innovation Summit 2024	Madrid, Spain
6	11-Nov-24	12-Nov-24	Fintech Talents Festival	London, UK
7	11-Nov-24	14-Nov-24	Web Summit	Lisbon, Portugal
8	19-Nov-24	22-Nov-24	Big Data Conference Europe 2024	Vilnius, Lithuania
9	20-Nov-24	21-Nov-24	SLUSH	Helsinki, Finland
10	4-Dec-24	6-Dec-24	Fintech Connect 2024	London, UK
11	3-Feb-25	3-Feb-25	Digital Assets Forum	London, UK
12	11-Feb-25	12-Feb-25	Stockholm Fintech Week	Stockholm, Sweden
13	25-Feb-25	26-Feb-25	Finovate Europe	London, UK
14	10-Mar-25	11-Mar-25	MoneyLIVE Summit	London, UK
15	19-Mar-25	20-Mar-25	Next Block Expo	Warsaw, Poland
16	25-Mar-25	26-Mar-25	Pay360 Conference	London, UK
17	28-Apr-25	2-May-25	UK FinTech Week	London, UK
18	29-Apr-25	29-Apr-25	Digisustain 2025	Frankfurt, Germany
19	15-May-25	15-May-25	Nordic Fintech Summit	Helsinki, Finland
20	2-Jun-25	6-Jun-25	2025 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain and Cryptocurrency (ICBC)	Pisa, Italy
21	4-Jun-25	6-Jun-25	Money 20/20 Europe	Amsterdam, The Netherlands
22	9-Jun-25	11-Jun-25	IEEE DCOSS-IoT	Lucca, Italy

23	16-Jun-25	18-Jun-25	European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS)	Amman, Jordan
24	16-Jun-25	20-Jun-25	SpliTech	Split, Croatia
25	7-Aug-25	9-Aug-25	2025 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Computer, Data Sciences and Applications (ACDSA)	Antalya, Turkiye
26	9-Sep-25	11-Sep-25	24th IFIP Conference e-Business, e-Services and e-Society	Limassol, Cyprus
27	9-Oct-25	13-Oct-25	IEEE International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)	Birmingham, UK
28	December 2025	December 2025	Fintech Connect 2025	TBD
29	October 2025	October 2025	European Big Data Value Forum 2025	TBD
30	Sep/Oct 2025	Sep/Oct 2025	European Blockchain Convention	Barcelona, Spain

3.4.3 List of relevant academic journals

The results of FAME will be relevant to the scientific community. Academic journals in the area of big data, digital finance, next generation technology applied to finance, etc. are an important means to disseminate the results of our project.

The table below presents a list of potential journals that could be targeted by FAME (non-exhaustive list):

Table 11: List of potential scientific journals

N°	Name of Journal	Main Topics
1	IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence	Machine intelligence
2	IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems	Neuronal network
3	Foundations and Trends in Machine Learning	ML
4	International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection	Critical infrastructure protection
5	International Journal of Information Technology & Decision Making	IT
6	Environmental Research Letter, the Journals of the Royal Statistical Society	Environmental research
7	International Journal of Information Security	Information security
8	ACM Transactions on Privacy and Security, IEEE Security and Privacy	Privacy and security data
9	Information Systems Frontiers (Springer)	Information system
10	International Journal of Information Management Data Insights (Elsevier)	Data Management

11	Behaviour & Information Technology (T&F)	IT
12	EPJ Data Science	Data science
13	Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence	AI
14	Evolving Systems	IT
15	International Journal of Data Science and Analytics	Data Science analytics

According to the EU rules, Open access to all the peer reviewed scientific publications of the project will be provided. Selected publications will be made available with the highest standard (Gold Open Access). The rest publications will be made available in the project's web site, but also in OpenAIRE's Zenodo open access repository. In terms of Open Peer review, FAME will allow self-selected reviewers to provide comments on the project's scientific outputs (i.e., publications, blueprints), beyond reviewers selected by the Open Access journals (or other forums) where the results will be made available. FAME partners will participate as open peer reviewers to open peer reviews of results from related projects (e.g., INFINITECH, TripleA, i3-MARKET) and projects funded in the same call. Open access to the FAME tools, trainings of the Learning Centre, videos, and feedback will ensure wide promotion/adoption as well.

The list is part of the Excel (section 3.2) added inside the FAME SharePoint which will be populated by the scientific / academic profile partners.

3.5 Communication and Dissemination Calendar for RP2

The FAME communication and dissemination calendar will provide partners with an overview of the different actions that will be organised during Reporting Period 2, covering M19-M36 of the project. The achievement of these tasks will require the collaboration of all partners. In the following table, the planned monthly communication and dissemination activities are presented with their indicative dates:

Table 12: Monthly Communication and Dissemination Activity Plan RP#2 (M19-36)

Qt.	Actual Month	Project Month	Activity	Indicative Timing	Channels	KPIs	Partner Contributions
Q3	July 2024	M19	G1 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	GFT, FTS, ATOS, IBM, ENG, MC, UNI, INNEUROPE
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			Newsletter 6	31 July 2024	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
	August 2024	M20	Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
	September 2024	M21	G2 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers) (3-4)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	DAEM, JRC, MOH, LXS, UBI, IQB, KM, UNP, CAGS
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
Newsletter 7			30 September 2024	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE	
Q4	October 2024	M22	G3 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	JOT, INNOV, TRB, NOVO, NUIG, NRS, NOVA, AL, EIH
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			EBDVF Event (organized/attendance, workshop, liason with other projects)	2-4 October 2024	Website (blog), Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter)	D1, D2, D3, C2	GFT, INNOV

		Finweek Bratislava (attendance, presentation)	22-24 October 2024	Website (blog), Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter)	D1, C2	EUBA, INNOV
		Newsletter 8	31 October 2024	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
		Website 2.0 Design	October 2024		C1/C4	INNEUROPE
November 2024	M23	G4 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	UPRC, JSI, EUBA, UIA, BPFI, ECO, IDSA, ETONEC
		Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
		FAME Webinar Series (LC): Webinar 1	11 November 2024	Webex (live), YouTube (recorded)	D7	INNOV, JSI
		FAME Webinar Series (LC): Webinar 2	27 November 2024	Webex (live), YouTube (recorded)	D7	INNOV, EUBA, UIA
		Website 2.0 Design	October 2024		C1/C4	INNEUROPE
		Newsletter 9	30 November 2024	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
December 2024	M24	G1 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	GFT, FTS, ATOS, IBM, ENG, MC, UNI, INNEUROPE
		Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
		FAME Webinar Series (LC): Webinar 3	2 December 2024	Webex (live), YouTube (recorded)	D7	INNOV, IBM
		Promo Video of UC/Tools (Pilot 7)	9 December 2024	YouTube	C5	ATOS, MOH
		Newsletter 10	31 December 2024	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
		Website 2.0 Implementation	December 2024	Website	C1/C4	INNEUROPE
Q4		Augment stakeholder database/engagement (LinkedIn +30 followers; X + 10 followers; Newsletter + 15 subscribers; stakeholder mapping +100)	Q4 2024	Social Media (LinkedIn, X), newsletter, database	C10	INNEUROPE, ALL

Q1	January 2025	M25	G2 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	DAEM, JRC, MOH, LXS, UBI, IQB, KM, UNP, CAGS
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			Brochure Version 2 and 3 (MVP & Pilot focus)	Mid-January 2025	Sharepoint	C7	INNEUROPE
			Website 2.0 Implementation	January 2024	Website	C1/C4	INNEUROPE
	February 2025	M26	G3 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	JOT, INNOV, TRB, NOVO, NUIG, NRS, NOVA, AL, EIH
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			Newsletter 11	28 February 2025	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
	March 2025	M27	G4 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	UPRC, JSI, EUBA, UIA, BPFI, ECO, IDSA, ETONEC
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			F2F Training	March 11-12 2025	Website (blog/news); Social Media (LinkedIn, X); YouTube	D7	INNOV
			Press Release: FAME Marketplace	31 March 2025	Media; partners' ecosystem	C9	INNEUROPE, ALL
			Use case demonstration Pilot 5	31 March 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	KM, JRC
			Use case workshop Pilot 5	31 March 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	KM, JRC
	Q1 2025		Revise C&D Calendar for upcoming quarters.	31 March 2025			INNEUROPE
			FAME Webinar Series (LC): Webinars 4-8	Q1 2025	Webex (live), YouTube (recorded)	D7, D15	INNOV
			Augment stakeholder database/engagement (LinkedIn +60 followers; X +30 followers; Newsletter +30 subscribers; stakeholder mapping +200)	Q1 2025	Social Media (LinkedIn, X), newsletter, database	C10	INNEUROPE, ALL
		Promo Video of UC/Tools (Pilot 7)	Q1 2025	YouTube	C5	ATOS, MOH	

Q2	April 2025	M28	G1 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	GFT, FTS, ATOS, IBM, ENG, MC, UNI, INNEUROPE
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			First use case demonstration and workshop Pilot 3	30 April 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	BPFI, NUIG, JRC
			Promo video Pilot 3 (version 2)	30 April 2025	Website, YouTube, Social Media	C5	BPFI, NUIG, JRC
			Newsletter 12	30 April 2025	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
	May 2025	M29	G2 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	DAEM, JRC, MOH, LXS, UBI, IQB, KM, UNP, CAGS
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			Use cases demonstration Pilot 1	30 May 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	MC, UNI, NOVA, UNP
			Use case 1 workshop Pilot 1	30 May 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	MC, UNI, NOVA, UNP
			Promo Video of UC/Tools (Pilot 1)	30 May 2025	Website, YouTube, Social Media	C5	MC, UNI, NOVA, UNP
			Promo Video of UC/Tools (Pilot 4)	30 May 2025	Website, YouTube, Social Media	C5	INNEUROPE
	June 2025	M30	G3 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	JOT, INNOV, TRB, NOVO, NUIG, NRS, NOVA, AL, EIH
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			Use Case Demonstration Pilot 4	9 June 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	INNEUROPE
			Use Case Workshop Pilot 4	9 June 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	INNEUROPE
			Use case 2 workshop Pilot 1	30 June 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	MC, UNI, NOVA, UNP
			Promo Video of UC/Tools (Pilot 6)	30 June 2025	Website, YouTube, Social Media	C5	NRS, GFT
			Newsletter 13	30 June 2025	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
			Revise C&D Calendar for upcoming quarters.	30 June 2025			INNEUROPE
	Q2 2025		Use Case demonstration/workshop Pilot 7	Q2 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	ATOS, MOH

		F2F Training	Q2 2025	Website (blog/news); Social Media (LinkedIn, X); YouTube	D7	INNOV	
		Dedicated ESG Results Promotion Event	Q2 2025	Website (blog/news); Social Media (LinkedIn, X); YouTube	D8	Pilot partners	
		Open Day with Use Cases (Policy makers and Banks)	Q2 2025	Website (blog/news); Social Media (LinkedIn, X); YouTube	D9	Pilot partners	
		Online event incorporating live survey/audience feedback	Q2 2025	Webex/Zoom/Teams	C3	ALL	
		Promo Video of UC/Tools (Pilot 2)	Q2 2025	YouTube	C5	NOVO, DAEM, UBI	
		Press release 1 for pilots 1-7	Q2 2025	Media; partners' ecosystem	C9	INNEUROPE, Pilot partners	
		Augment stakeholder database/engagement (LinkedIn +60 followers; X +30 followers; Newsletter +30 subscribers; stakeholder mapping +200)	Q2 2025	Social Media (LinkedIn, X), newsletter, database	C10	INNEUROPE, ALL	
Q3	July 2025	M31	G4 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	UPRC, JSI, EUBA, UIA, BPFI, ECO, IDSA, ETONEC
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			Second use case demonstration and workshop Pilot 3	31 July 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	BPFI, NUIG, JRC
	August 2025	M32	G1 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	GFT, FTS, ATOS, IBM, ENG, MC, UNI, INNEUROPE
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
			Promo Video of UC/Tools (Pilot 5)	31 August 2025	Website, YouTube, Social Media	C5	KM, JRC
			Newsletter 14	31 August 2025	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
	September 2025	M33	G2 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	DAEM, JRC, MOH, LXS, UBI, IQB, KM, UNP, CAGS

			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL	
			Use Case Demonstration Pilot 6	30 September 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	NRS, GFT	
			Use Case Workshop Pilot 6	30 September 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	NRS, GFT	
			Revise C&D Calendar for upcoming quarters.	30 September 2025			INNEUROPE	
	Q3 2025			Dedicated ESG Results Promotion Event 2	Q3 2025	Website (blog/news); Social Media (LinkedIn, X); YouTube	D8	Pilot partners
				Open Day with Use Cases (Policy makers and Banks)	Q3 2025	Website (blog/news); Social Media (LinkedIn, X); YouTube	D9	Pilot partners
				Use case demonstration/workshop Pilot 2	Q3 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	NOVO, DAEM, UBI
				Press release 2 for pilots 1-7	Q3 2025	Media; partners' ecosystem	C9	INNEUROPE, Pilot partners
	Q4	October 2025	M34	G3 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	JOT, INNOV, TRB, NOVO, NUIG, NRS, NOVA, AL, EIH
				Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
Q4	November 2025	M35	Third use case demonstration and workshop Pilot 3	31 October 2025	Social Media, Website	D6	BPFI, NUIG, JRC	
			Newsletter 15	31 October 2025	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE	
Q4	November 2025	M35	G4 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	UPRC, JSI, EUBA, UIA, BPFI, ECO, IDSA, ETONEC	
			Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL	

December 2025	M36	G1 Content Contributions (blog, news, whitepapers)	2/week	Website (blog/news)	C2	GFT, FTS, ATOS, IBM, ENG, MC, UNI, INNEUROPE
		Dissemination of project updates on social media (LC, Marketplace, pilots, events, articles, etc.)	2-3/week	Social Media (LinkedIn, X)	C6	INNEUROPE, ALL
		Promo video Pilot 3 (version 3)	15 December 2025	Website, YouTube, Social Media	C5	BPFI, NUIG, JRC
		Newsletter 16	31 December 2025	Newsletter	C9	INNEUROPE
Q4 2025		Augment stakeholder database/engagement (LinkedIn +60 followers; X +30 followers; Newsletter +30 subscribers; stakeholder mapping +200)	Q4 2025	Social Media (LinkedIn, X), newsletter, database	C10	INNEUROPE, ALL

4 Conclusions

The overall communication and dissemination strategy and plan for the FAME project has been established and explained throughout this deliverable. Divided into two main sections, the first part of the document (*Section 2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy*) defined the project's target groups, online and offline tools, available channels, KPIs and communication guidelines. FAME's online tools (LinkedIn, X, YouTube, the project website and newsletters/press releases) will be used to further disseminate the progress made within the framework of the project, as well as provide key opportunities for the targeted stakeholders to be involved (e.g., accessing the FAME Marketplace or LC, using FAME resources, analysing FAME publications, etc.). Internally, the FAME logo, brand manual and other internal communication materials (brochure, flyers, roller, etc.) will be used by project partners to further disseminate the project and its expected results.

Likewise, the second part (*Section 3 Communication and Dissemination Plan*) displays the coordination plan, individual partner intentions, opportunities for European events and academic journals, and a planned calendar for RP2. While the first part outlines FAME's official social media channels (LinkedIn, X), the overview of the website and YouTube channel, a key component to successfully carrying out communication and dissemination activities derives from each partner organization. For this reason, each partner will utilize their specific channels (organization websites and social media, events (workshops, conferences, exhibitions, etc.), publication, webinars, blog articles, internal newsletters, internal stakeholder networks, etc.) to further disseminate FAME and reach a larger network, resulting in the creation of a large community/ecosystem around the project's results.

Following the technical review, certain revisions were made to this deliverable to align efforts for the second reporting period (RP2). Section 2.2.3 was updated to include the new design of the project website, prior to release 2.0. Stated in brief in this deliverable, more specifics of the new design can be found in D7.2. Next, the individual partner communication and dissemination intentions (Section 3.3) was updated to remove past partners who have left the project and incorporate new partners who were not included in the original table. Likewise, where necessary and appropriate, the strategic focus of some partners was updated to give specific reference to the pilot projects. Thirdly, the list of strategic European events for RP2 (Section 3.4.2) was included, highlighting the opportunities available to present FAME, its Marketplace and LC, as well as the different pilots at various European conferences, summits, and workshops. Finally, Section 3.5 encompasses a comprehensive communication and dissemination plan for RP2 that will guide all efforts from M19-M36, including indicative timelines for each action. This plan not only includes routine actions, such as content generation for the project website (e.g., news articles, blog posts, publications of whitepapers, etc.) and regular communication on FAME's social media channels, but also it includes specific actions related to the Marketplace, LC and pilots, such as the planned release of the Marketplace, planned demonstration events and workshops for the pilots, creation of promo videos and the publication of press releases. This plan will be revisited each quarter to make any necessary updates, narrow the focus, and remind partners of commitments.